

Methodology for improving the physical and technical preparation of belt wrestlers at the initial training stage

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Abstract

This article identifies current challenges in the development of physical and technical preparation for belt wrestlers at the initial training stage and provides scientifically-based recommendations for addressing them. The research was conducted through surveys with coaches and pedagogical experiments at sports schools in the city of Nukus. The results indicate that planning training sessions with consideration for age-specific characteristics, the gradual distribution of loads, and the sequential teaching of technical methods effectively develops the preparedness of belt wrestlers.

Keywords: belt wrestlers, initial preparation, physical preparation, training loads, pedagogical supervision.

Introduction

In recent years, the continuous improvement of athletic performance in prestigious global competitions, including the World and Asian Championships, as well as several traditional international tournaments, has led to increasingly fierce competition. Sports science experts have noted that in modern athletic practice, exceeding the standard volume and intensity of training loads to achieve high results can lead to undesirable consequences and even injuries. The sequential teaching of dynamic games and technical methods used to develop the physical fitness of belt wrestlers in the initial training stage has not been sufficiently explored from a scientific standpoint. This necessitates that specialists conduct scientifically-grounded research on the matter.

Extensive scientific research is being conducted worldwide on studying and improving the developmental stages of physical qualities in belt wrestlers, selecting talented athletes, planning and monitoring training loads, and the impact of physical and psychophysiological loads on the bodies of children and adolescents involved in belt wrestling. The formation of motivation for sports engagement necessitates improving the role and effectiveness of active games in retaining the athlete contingent. Improving and

implementing the training tools and methods used to develop the physical and technical preparedness of belt wrestlers at the initial training stage, while considering their age-specific characteristics, remains one of the pressing issues facing qualified coaches and industry specialists today.

In our republic, one of the key issues in the field of physical education and sports is ensuring the regular participation of the population in sports, as well as establishing a new system for identifying, selecting, and training talented athletes to become professionals. Particular attention is being paid to the "implementation of systemic measures for the development and popularization of national sports, and their inclusion in the programs of the Asian and Olympic Games." The proper planning of training sessions aimed at developing the physical and technical preparedness of belt wrestlers at the initial training stage, creating optimal training microcycles, and developing exercises and methods to be used in training remain pressing issues.

When training belt wrestlers, it is crucial to plan sessions on a scientific basis, distribute workloads progressively, and establish pedagogical supervision. Taking into account the individual characteristics of athletes and personalizing the training process are important factors in the effective mastery of technical-tactical actions and the development of specialized work capacity.[4, p. 42].

The aim of the study is to develop proposals and recommendations for improving the technical and physical training of belt wrestlers at the initial training stage.

Organization of the Study. The study was conducted in the city of Nukus based on questionnaires distributed to coaches of qualified belt wrestlers. The main purpose of this organized interview was to obtain information about the training process for young belt wrestlers in the initial preparatory stage at sports schools, as well as the relevant

Table 1. Results of a questionnaire survey of coaches who conduct training sessions for young belt wrestlers at the initial preparatory stage

Responses	Qualified coaches	n=40
Question 1. <i>At what age do you consider it appropriate to admit wrestlers to the initial stage of belt wrestling training?</i>		
A	From age 7	25%
B	From age 9	50%
C	From age 8	25%
Question 2. <i>During the training process, which qualities do you focus on developing most in belt wrestlers at the initial preparatory stage?</i>		
A	Flexibility, agility, speed	80%
B	Strength, endurance, speed	10%
C	Strength, speed, flexibility	10%
Question 3. <i>Which areas of preparation do you consider it appropriate to focus on for belt wrestlers at the initial preparatory stage?</i>		
A	Physical preparation, technical preparation	65%
B	Technical and tactical preparation	25%
C	Psychological and technical preparation	10%
Question 4. <i>Which muscle groups do you believe should be better developed in belt wrestlers during the initial preparation stage?</i>		
A	Arm and shoulder girdle muscles	30%
B	Leg (thigh and calf) muscles	20%
C	Arm, lower back, and leg muscles	50%
Question 5. <i>What methods do you most often use for the recovery of belt wrestlers' bodies after training sessions?</i>		
A	Sleep, massage	80%
B	Wellness tourism	10%
C	Shower, swimming	10%

documentation and the tools and methods used in training. In addition, the results of a questionnaire survey conducted among the coaches who participated in the meeting to identify the most important aspects of the current training process are presented in Table 1 below.

Results and discussion

When we analyzed the results of the first question of the survey, in response to our question, "At what age do you consider it appropriate to admit belt wrestlers to the initial preparation stage?" 25% of the coaches answered

"from age 7," 25% of the coaches answered "from age 8," while 50% of the coaches answered "from age 9." It is advisable to involve Greco-Roman wrestlers in the training process starting from the age of 9 at the initial preparation stage.

If the answer is from the age of 8, 50% of the coaches answered from the age of 9. At the initial training stage, it is advisable to involve Greco-Roman wrestlers in the training process starting from the age of 9.

In response to the second question of our survey, "Which qualities do you focus on developing most in belt wrestlers during the initial training stage?," 80% of coaches answered flex-

Table 3. Total indicators of belt wrestlers at the initial training stage in the experimental and control groups (n=36)

No.	Total and partial indicators of athletes	Experimental Group			Control Group		
		\pm	σ	V%	$\bar{X} \pm$	σ	V%
1	Height (cm)	135.3	7.7	5.9	136.8	5.1	3.9
2	Weight (kg)	33.2	5.4	12.7	34.6	4.5	11.9
3	Chest circumference at rest (cm)	62.6	11.5	14.1	63.8	4.5	6.8
4	Right hand grip strength (kg)	16.9	1.1	6.3	17.1	1.5	5.8
5	Left hand grip strength (kg)	16.5	1.3	5.7	16.8	1.4	4.9

ibility, agility, and speed. 10% of coaches responded with strength, endurance, and speed, while the remaining 10% of coaches cited strength, speed, and flexibility.

For the third question of our survey, "Which aspects of training do you consider most appropriate to focus on for belt wrestlers in the initial training stage?," 65% of coaches indicated physical and technical training. 25% of coaches responded with technical-tactical training, while 10% of coaches answered psychological and technical training.

In response to the fourth question of our survey, "Which muscle groups do you believe need to be better developed in belt wrestlers during the initial training stage?," 30% of coaches answered the arm and shoulder girdle muscles. 20% of coaches cited the leg muscles (thigh and calf), while 50% of coaches responded with the arm and leg muscles.

In our questionnaire's fifth question, "What methods do you most often use to help

wrestlers' bodies recover after training?," 80% of the coaches answered "sleep and massage," 10% answered "wellness tourism," and the remaining 10% answered "showering and swimming."

The questions in our aforementioned questionnaire were designed to identify the defined tasks. Based on the results obtained, we used the "POLAR H10" device to determine the volume and intensity of the training loads given to children in the initial training group at Sports School No. 1 in Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan. Through this device, we identified both the age-appropriate and inappropriate aspects of the volume and intensity of training loads given to the young belt wrestlers in this group.

As shown in Table 3, the average results of belt wrestlers in the control group at the initial training stage for the 30 m run test were 6.4 seconds, while the experimental group's result

Table 3. Indicators of general and special physical fitness of belt wrestlers in the initial training stage of the experimental and control groups at the beginning of the experiment (n=36)

No.	Indicators of general and special physical fitness	Experimental group			Control group		
		\pm	σ	V%	$\bar{X} \pm$	σ	V%
1	30 m dash (s).	6.6	0.2	3.6	6.4	0.3	2.3
2	3x10 m shuttle run (s).	8.5	8.6	2.6	8.3	0.2	2.3
3	Standing long jump (cm).	140.1	0.2	5.3	139.6	0.6	4.2
4	Push-ups (reps).	15.5	2.1	6.3	14.7	3.8	14.8
5	Pull-ups (reps)	3.6	0.8	10.2	3.1	0.9	10.6
6	Running in a circle from a bridge position, 5 times to the right and 5 times to the left (seconds)	25.1	0.8	4.6	26.2	0.6	4.4
7	10 head jumps from a bridge position (seconds)	18.9	0.4	4.5	18.5	0.7	4.3

Table 4. The sequence of teaching technical techniques to belt wrestlers in the initial training stage

No.	Name of techniques	Difficulty of teaching techniques
<i>Sequence of teaching technical techniques</i>		
1	Side throw	1
2	Hooking throw	2
3	Right hip throw	3
4	Left hip throw	4
5	Right knee lift-throw	5
6	Left knee lift-throw	6
7	Front lift and hip throw	7
8	Chest throw	8

was 5.6 seconds. In the 3x10 m maximum sprint test, the belt wrestlers in the control group at the initial training stage scored 8.3 seconds, while the experimental group scored 8.5 seconds. In the standing long jump test for belt wrestlers, the control group athletes' result was 139.6 cm, while the experimental group's was 140.1 cm. For the push-up test (number of repetitions), the control group athletes performed 14.7 repetitions, while the experimental group performed 15.5 repetitions. In the pull-up test (number of repetitions), the control group athletes performed 3.1 repetitions, and the experimental group performed 3.6 repetitions. For the test involving running in a circle from a bridge position (5 times to the right, 5 times to the left), the average result for belt wrestlers in the control group was 25.1 seconds, while the experimental group's was 26.2 seconds. For the test involving 10 jumps over the head from a bridge position (seconds), the belt wrestlers in the control group had a result of 18.9 seconds, while the experimental group's was 18.5 seconds.

We developed a sequential method for teaching technical skills to belt wrestlers at the initial training stage.

Belt wrestling athletes in the initial training stage must master technical techniques with the following descriptions: side throw, hooking throw, right hip throw, left hip throw, right knee lift-throw, left knee lift-throw, front lift and hip throw, and chest throw (Table 4).

A series of pedagogical experiments were conducted to assess the physical preparedness of belt wrestlers at the initial training stage.

The study participants, belt wrestlers at the initial training stage, were divided into two groups. Group 1 was the control group (18 individuals); its members were tested in 2025 using the control test exercises mentioned below and continued to participate in training sessions from the first day of observation.

Group 2 was the pedagogical research group (18 individuals). This group was also tested alongside Group 1, and for six months in 2025, targeted methods were used to develop the physical fitness of the research group.

We analyzed the total indicators, level of physical development, and body composition characteristics of the belt wrestlers at the initial training stage in the experimental and control groups involved in our study.

The total indicators of the belt wrestlers at the initial training stage were determined at the beginning of the study and are presented in Table 2 below.

According to this, the total indicators for the 36 athletes selected for the experimental and control groups were expressed as follows. The average body height of the athletes in the experimental group was 135.3 cm, while in the control group, this indicator averaged 136.8 cm. The average weight of the athletes in the experimental group was 33.2 kg, while in the control group, it averaged 34.6 kg. It was determined that the chest circumference at rest was 62.6 cm in the experimental group, while in the control group athletes, it averaged 63.8 cm. Right-hand strength (kg) was determined to be 16.9 kg for the experimental group athletes and an average of 17.1 kg for the control group athletes. Left-hand strength (kg) was determined to be 16.5 kg for the experimental group athletes and an average of 16.8 kg for the control group athletes.

As a result of the analysis, no statistically significant differences were identified at the beginning of the pedagogical experiment between the studied parameters of the belt wrestlers in the initial training stage of the experimental and control groups (see Table 3).

Conclusion

Based on an analysis of best practices

and scientific-methodological literature, a sequence for improving the methods and tools at the initial training stage was established, grounded in the sequence and interaction of technical maneuvers performed by the belt wrestlers under study. For belt wrestlers in the initial training phase, teaching stances first, followed by the mastery of technical maneuvers, is significantly more effective when learned in the following order: first, learn to execute attacks, then defense, and subsequently, counter-attacks. After this, one should focus on mastering these skills and transitioning to the next phase.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the development of physical fitness in young belt wrestlers at the initial training stage is achieved through the rational planning of the annual training plan, its objectives, cyclical structure, special exercises, active games, and recovery measures.

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Research interests

physical education and sport, Theory of physical education, Analyzing of sport competitions